

The Effectiveness Of Employing Telegram Application In Teaching Vocabulary: A Quasai Experimental Study

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: March 29, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: June 23,2020</p> <p>Keywords : Arab EFL learners Telegram app Social nets work Vocabulary learning</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3905099</p>	<p><i>Technology usage has become a crucial factor in learning English in and out of the classroom. Nowadays, English classroom utilizing digital technology application. Digital technologies have been utilized to improve and help teaching and learning the language. Digital technologies helped educators to adapt modern teaching methods, therefore, improve the process of teaching and learning the English language. This paper investigates the effect of using digital technology (Telegram) on EFL students' vocabulary learning. 40 Arab high school pre-intermediate EFL students at Arabic International School in Kuala Lumpur were selected. Using a quasi-experimental design, the data was collected through a placement test, pre-post-test. Students were divided into control and experimental groups. The experimental group received their lessons through Telegram. However, the control group practised conventional teaching methods. The data of the experimental post-test showed that Telegram is an effective teaching tool that motivates students to learn vocabulary enjoyably. Implications and recommendations are drawn at the end of the paper.</i></p>

Introduction

According to Moerira et al. (2016), it found to be a development among educators and experts regarding utilization of cell phones in the learning-teaching environment as a result of their capacity, flexibility, and the versatility to aid cultivate singular learning encounters. Mobile devices may develop productive learning by the students in which stated by (Vavoula & Sharples, 2008) "where learners show responsibility for and initiate their learning, share learning with experts and peers". Mobile devices enable the learners to enjoy the new learning environments like pedagogy (Petersen et al, 2008; Benson & Chik, 2010) which means the learning is student-centred (Hayati et al, 2013). In light of this, mobile learning enables and improves learner-centred approach in line with the widespread of wireless networks and mobile devices that include tablets and smartphones (Karpisek et al 2015). Voted as one of the most well-known portable ambassadors by "Most famous versatile informing applications," (2017), "WhatsApp" is a platform utilized for calls, messaging and sharing content such as images, audio etc. It is accessible on various portable stages including all mobile phones systems. One of the other popular online applications used is Telegram which was launched in 2013 by Pavel and Nikolai Durov, a business visionary and a software engineer, situated in Berlin. Telegram is a user-friendly application as it is easy to use with the advantages of embedded stickers in their system. This application can be used to download and receive assorted documents with different capacity compared to WhatsApp. Telegram is a various stage application that can run on, iOS, Android, Phone, Windows, and Mac. According to Ebrahimi et al (2016) Telegram can be utilized in different devices simultaneously. Telegram allows users to create groups of up to 5000 people for broadcasting to infinite audiences (Vivienne, 2016). As indicated by Niayesh (2015), the quantity of Iranians who use Telegram has driven this versatile informal community application to be an observer of a tremendous blast and further clarifies that if local informal organizations draw in more clients as Telegram did, it will be useful for the nation especially towards the society and economy. The tremendous reception wave came after Iranian clients experienced various disadvantages while getting to other mainstream informal community applications, specifically, Viber or Whatsapp.

Schmitt (2008) found that teaching EFL jargon can be characterized as "words we should know to impart adequately" (Neuman and Dwyer, 2009), which implies that jargon ought to be considered as more than a lot of single-word units. Presently, it is practically difficult to gain proficiency in a language without words; even correspondence among people depends on words (Walters, 2004). A broad jargon would permit us to utilize the structures and capacities for understandable correspondence (Nation, 2012). Instructing words is a fundamental angle when learning a language as dialects depend on words (Thornbury, 2002). Truth be told, in English as a Second Language (ESL) and EFL, learning jargon things assumes an essential job in the procurement of the four language aptitudes – listening, speaking, reading, and writing (Nation, 2011). Stahl and Shiel (1992) express that jargon guidance straightforwardly improves perception. They call attention to that it is significant for understudies to have a profound comprehension of scholarly jargon to grasp new ideas and convey what we know. Subsequently, the securing of fitting jargon is the centre for effective language use. Concerning and unknown dialect jargon obtaining, familiarity and exactness are significant angles to be created. Right now, the PPP approach is a typical technique to educate jargon. For instance, in the introduction organize, there are a few choices that can be utilized to present jargon, for example, realia, pictures, activities, motions, definitions, interpretation and circumstances (Thornbury, 2002). The training stage should create precision through oral and composed activities, responsive profitable assignments, individual and gathering exercises. In the creation arrangement, which is proposed to create familiarity, the exercises are centred around evoking the recently learned words (Criado, 2013).

Method

The study employed a quasi-experimental research design to examine the effectiveness of utilising Telegram application in teaching English among Arab EFL students. Likewise, the study measured the learners' attitudes towards using Telegram for vocabulary learning. The participants of the study were 50 Arab EFL the 9th grader's students in one Arabic international school in Kuala Lumpur in the studying year 2019-2020. Arabic is the native language of the students. The availability and convenience sampling technique were used to select the participants. A placement test was distributed to test the students' proficiency. Then, the pre-test was given to the learners. The test contained 50 multiple-choice questions. The test was sent to four university professors to review and edit regarding validity. The test reliability KR-20 was ($r=.78$) with a group of 10 student's at the same level of proficiency of the participants of the current research. The post-test took place on the last day of the project. A panel of experts in English language teaching approved and validated the test and its KR-20 reliability was .81. The treatment group undertook 12 meetings with the intervention of ICT usage of Telegram application group discussion integrated into every single lesson of the meeting over 12 weeks. In data analysis, the researchers used SPSS.20 paired-sample t-test. Before the conduction of the paired-sample t-test, its assumption was checked.

Results and Findings

In this section, the results of the data collected from the student will be presented

1. Demographic Information

Table.1 Findings of Demographic information

No. of Students	40 students	
Gender	30- Male, 10 Female	
Age	15-18	
Owning a handphone?	N	%
Yes	36	90
No	4	10
Technology usage for learning purposes	N	%
never used	4	10%
less than 6 months	100	50.0
Around 1 year	70	35
around 2-3 years	20	10.

Access	N	%
I access the internet at home	37	94
I access the internet at cybercafé	30	75
I access the internet at school	10	25
Screen Time	N	%
0-15 hours	11	30
16-30 hours	29	70
Preferred Teaching Style	N	%
Modern/ technology based	30	75
Traditional/ Teacher centred	10	25

The findings of demographic information, placement test, pre, and post-test and attitude questionnaire answers are presented. The percentages and frequencies number of students, of gender, age, availability of internet access, access types, screen time, phone type owned, activities types and preferred teaching style are presented. Data showed that (75%, n=30) of the respondents are male while (25% n=10) are female. As for age, findings showed that the students' age goes between 14 to 15 years old. The majority of the students own a handphone (90%, n=36). As for using technology for learning purposes, (75%, n=30) use technology devices to learn for less than 6 months. Moreover, data showed that the majority of the students have internet access (95% n=37) at home. This means that students can easily access their learning material anytime anywhere making the learning process easier. Not surprisingly, as a Z generation, respondents spend a long time on screen, as data showed (70% n=29) spend 21-30 hours per week on the internet. Lastly, regarding the preferred teaching style, (75%, n=30) of the respondents prefer the modern style of teaching which is technology-based teaching. This means the students are aware of the effective role of this teaching style.

Result of Placement Test

The respondents of this research were a beginner high school level students. However, to ensure their homogeneity, these researchers calculated measures and scores of the descriptive statistics of the placement test. Therefore, the criteria for selecting the participants was based on the scores ranged between below and above the mean and one standard deviation. The researchers didn't employ any inferential statistics as a single group of EFL learners was selected to participate in the experimental, descriptive statistics are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics of the Placement Test

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis
Placement Test	40	2.00	8.00	4.50	3.58	-.001	-1.29

Participants' number ($N = 40$), the mean score ($M = 4.50$), standard deviation ($SD = 3.58$). As showed, students with a score ranged from 3.00 and 9.00 were classified as for beginners so they can participate in this study. Moreover, the table presented the values of skewness and kurtosis tests. The 0 value of skewness and kurtosis have resulted in the distribution is perfectly normal. As the table shows, the value of skewness was a little negative (-.001), indicating a slight scores clustering at the high right-hand end of the distribution (negatively skewed). The kurtosis value, as showed in table 2, (-1.20) indicates that the distribution was slightly flat.

Results of Pre-Test and Post-Test.

Table 3 Tests of Normality

GROUP	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Si

The pre-test data of both class	PRETEST	CONTROL CLASS	.157	25	.113	.943	25
			EXPERIMENTAL CLASS	.113	25	.200*	.954

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

*This is a lower bound of the true significance.

es, presented in the above table, were found to be normally distributed as the Asymp Sig. of the data in the Kolmogorov-Smirnov column is higher than 0.05. For instance, the experimental class probability value (Asymp.Sig) is 0.200 while the control class (Asymp. Sig) is 0.112. indicating that the distributions of pre-tests in both classes are normal. Furthermore, Levenes' test is used to analyse the homogeneity of the variance by comparing the Asymp. sigs. at the significance level at 0.05. So, the probability should be >0.05; thus, the variance of the classes should be homogeneous.

Table 4 Test of Homogeneity of Variances

PRETEST			
Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
.508	1	48	.480

As the table shows, the probability of score in the pre-test is higher than 0.05 (0.480>0.05). it means that the variances of both classes are homogeneous.

Independent t-test

To show the significant differences between the mean of the class in the pre-test, the independent t-test formula in SPSS 22.0 was used for the analysis. Moreover, to reject the null hypothesis, measures should be taken to compare credit and to be at the level of 0.05 and df=48 (2.021). Besides, rejecting the null hypothesis means there is a difference between the mean of the two classes (tobt>tcrit). In opposite, if the hypothesis is accepted then there is not any difference of means between the two classes (tobt<tcrit).

Table 5 Group Statistics

Group	N	Mean	S D	S.Error Me
PRETEST Control class	25	49.94	12.069	2.414
Experimental class	25	52.80	11.100	2.220

According to t-test table 3, there are differences in the mean score of the experimental class (52.8) and control class (49.94). While that is 0.871 which means that is smaller than the script (0.871<2.021). Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted (H0) which indicates no significant difference in means scores of the pre-test among experimental and control groups.

The result of Post-test

The analyzing procedure of the post-test was similar to the pre-test. Besides; the post-test measures the students' improvement in vocabulary mastery after conducting the treatment and expose the differences whether there is any difference in scores between two classes or not.

The normality distribution test

The measurement of the normal distribution of the post-test is performed by the Kolmogorov-Smirnov in SPSS 16.0 to see whether the scores are normally distributed or not. When the data are normally distributed, they can be compared using the parametric statistics; for instance, simple t-test, and if they are not normally distributed, then they can be analyzed further with nonparametric statistics such as Wilcoxon test. The post-test normality is the results presented in table 6.

Table 6. Test of normality distribution

GROUP	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a		Shapiro-Wilk	
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic

POSTTEST	CONTROL CLASS	.129	25	.20	.966 25	.5
	EXPERIMENTAL CLASS	.137	25	.20	.960 25	.4

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

*. This is a lower bound of the true significance.

Table 4 reveals that the post-test data of the control class and experimental class are normally distributed because the Asymp Sig. of the data in KolmogorovSmirnov column is greater than 0.05 ($0.544 > 0.05$ and $0.409 > 0.05$). To measure the homogeneity of the variance, Asymp.sig with the significance level at 0.05 should be compared. Table 5. Test of homogeneity

Table.7 Test of Homogeneity of Variances.

Test of Homogeneity of Variances				
POSTTEST				
Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.	
.013	1	48	.910	

According to the findings in table 5, the probability of score in the post-test is higher than 0.05 ($0.910 > 0.05$). It means that the variances of both classes are homogeneous.

Independent t-test of post-test

To find out the fundamental differences among the mean scores of experimental and control classes in the post-test, the data are analyzed by independent t-test. Rejecting the null hypothesis (H_0) means there is no significant difference between the two classes. The next step is to compare between that and script at the level of 0.05 and $df = 48$ (2.021). Also, if the null hypothesis is rejected, which indicates the mean scores' difference between the two classes ($t_{obt} > t_{crit}$). However, if the hypothesis is accepted, then there is no difference in the mean scores among the groups ($t_{obt} < t_{crit}$).

GROUP	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
POSTTEST CONTROL CLASS	25	58.06	11.118	2.224
EXPERIMENTAL CLASS	25	65.03	11.317	2.263

POSTTEST	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig.(2-tailed)	Mean Diff	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval of the Lower	Upper	
Equal variances assumed		.013	.910	-	48	.033	-6.971	3.173	-13.351	.5
	2.197									
Equal variances not assumed				-	47.98	.033	-6.971	3.173	-13.351	-.5
	5				2.197					

As shown in Table 6, the mean score of the control group is (58.06) and the mean score of the experimental group is (65.03). Moreover, that is (2.197), which means to be is greater than credit (2.197>2.02). Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected (H0). It means that there are essential differences in the mean scores of the experimental and control groups in the post-test.

The paired t-test

The paired t-test was used to measure the scores of the experimental group through SPSS 16.0 for windows. It was aimed to see the mean scores differences among the two tests. The result provided below:

Paired Samples Statistics				
	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	51.37	50	11.566	1.636
	61.54	50	11.648	1.647

As table shown, the mean score of the pre-test in experimental class is (51.37), while the mean score of post-test is (61.54). Including this, the significance of the 2 tailed is 0.00, which is smaller than 0.05 (0.00<0.05).

Paired Samples Correlations			
Pair 1		N	Correlation
Pair 1	PRETEST & POSTTEST	50	.807

Based on the findings above, it is revealed that the null hypothesis is refused; which means there was a difference in the post-test and pre-test scores after the treatment.

Discussion

Based on the findings, the reason post-test has a higher mean than the pre-test is due to learning vocabulary during the session via the use of Wiki. With the help of technology, the students were able to learn the English vocabulary, their definitions, and verbs as well as imaginatively describing detailed pictures. It is in line with Marazano's vocabulary learning strategy in which according to Scurletis (2009) that understudies ought to portray, clarify, give a non-phonetic definition, discuss, and enjoy learning new vocabulary. As for this research, the participants were not provided with an advance vocabulary practice during their session. The researchers observed the class to see whether it runs with the formal or informal curriculum and found that the class regularly focused on vocabulary improvement in which was proven by (Khany, R. & Khosravian, F 2014; Sadikin 2016; and Eren 2015) that reports the statistically remarkable difference in language learners' vocabulary development. Based on their findings, they found that ICT platforms are beneficial to students in encouraging original resources to alleviate their vocabulary knowledge. The study aimed at investigating the effect of Telegram on teaching English vocabulary, as an online learning platform with many benefits that include sharing information swiftly and utilize it to also learning vocabulary for Arabic EFL Beginners. The results assured the fact that there was a noticeable difference among the scores of the students in the two groups of the different test techniques. As the results showed, the scores of the words were taught utilising telegram ($M = 17.54$) were outstandingly higher than that of conventional educated words ($M = 15.38$).

As it were, the Telegram online platform is a powerful and helpful asset for enhancing the jargon information on the Arab EFL learners. The past investigations identified with utilizing interpersonal organizations, for example, Tweeter, Zoom, Line are following these outcomes. The results are on-line with Selwyn (2003) who referenced digital technologies is being utilized in training to assist learners with learning successfully and help instructors to do managerial assignments effectively. Moreover, these discoveries are additionally in concurrence with (Lomicka & Lord, 2011; Yapici & Hevedanli 2014) that expressed more youthful individuals spend an impressive bit of their mundane life communicating through online networking; these locales have

become a significant piece of most students' lives. The aftereffects of the current investigation are likewise under those of (Ghaemi and Golshan2017). Besides, the examination results bolster the results of Jones et al (2010) which referenced that interpersonal organizations can create formal learning and become some portion of the instructive condition of students. The outcomes are per discoveries of (Hakim 2019; Kabilan 2010; and Girgin2011).

since they exhibited that informal organizations, for example, Telegram, Facebook, and Tweeter could be used as an online circumstance to encourage the learning of diverse English language abilities. In light of the discoveries, Telegram can upgrade cooperation of understudies out of the study hall and it can support students and educators by making friends, a private, intriguing and far-reaching connection among instructors and students out of the homeroom. Components in the literature review suggest the significance of implementing ICT in English classrooms to improve teaching and learning (Hubbard, 2003). Studies have shown that if ICT can be coordinated effectively, it can fundamentally improve students' scholarly presentation, especially students' vocabulary abilities (Alazamet al, 2012; Nair et al., 2008). The after-effects of the current investigation demonstrate that in the timeframe, the mix of ICT in the conventional up close and personal English class can fundamentally improve students' language capability. Be that as it may, further examinations with more extensive examples, treatments should be done to affirm these discoveries. What's more, this present examination likewise found that ICT can encourage an increasingly positive, strong and favourable learning condition which eventually helps understudies' inspiration to find out additional. This is by the past investigation discoveries (e.g Sun and Metros, 2011; Kean, Embi, and Yunus, 2012).

Conclusion

The aimed of this study to examine the effect of utilizing Telegram on EFL student's lexicon learning. Also, the study aimed to unearth the students' attitude towards the use of Telegram in learning English vocabulary. The tools utilized in this study post-test, an online stage called telegram and pre-test. To conclude, this study revealed that social media such as telegram have an extremely essential effect on learning English vocabulary. Based on their results, the researchers showed that ICT platforms are beneficial to students in encouraging original resources to alleviate their vocabulary knowledge. The researches found how the telegram utilise positively to facilitate the process of learning and interaction outside the classroom environment. Besides, the researchers demonstrated that there are some limitations or restriction related to age, gender, and race are limited to our small group and many other restrictions related to gender as not allowed for the female to utilize technology in the Arabic countries especially for the teenagers that age begin from 13-18 years.

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